

Tutorial Script: Using Copilot as a Scrum Master

Introduction (5 minutes)

Hello everyone. In this tutorial session, we will explore how Copilot can be used as an assistant for Scrum Masters managing agile projects.

Copilot in Bing is an AI-powered enhancement to the Microsoft Bing search engine. It understands and generates human-like responses to user queries. It can summarize information, answer questions, generate ideas, and even provide explanations across various topics. This makes it a potential tool for conversational assistance with information gathering and decision-making, like in the role of a Scrum Master in Agile Teams. Copilot integrates into the Bing interface, and it complies with GDPR under the Kristiania user account.

Some of the examples I will introduce here were drawn from our fictional project case. Smart Tourist Network (STN) is a mobile application for tourists visiting Oslo that want to explore the city. By specifying the time in hours and locations to be visited, the app smartly establishes a schedule for the tourist based on provided time.

The SM facilitates Scrum processes by acting as a servant leader to the team. Their responsibilities are (1) ensure that the team adheres to Scrum practices, (2) offer support to optimize productivity, (3) remove impediments to the team's progress, (4) make Scrum events productive and within time limits, (5) help team members understand their roles within the project.

Copilot Access

Show how to access the Copilot via Kristiania's Bing environment: <https://copilot.microsoft.com/> or <https://www.bing.com/>. Remember students to use their Kristiania user account.

Perform a simple test to ensure Copilot is responding, such as "What are the responsibilities of a Scrum Master?"

In the final report/reflection notes you are to reflect on the process and tools you have used. Therefore, you should save your prompts and responses to be able to reflect on them regarding how they have affected your work in the project and include example excerpts. This will also help us in assessing the potential advantages and limitations of AI within this course.

Main Content: Scrum Master Tasks with Copilot (20 minutes)

Starting with Daily Scrum

Prompt: "Our team is new to Scrum and we're just getting started with our first sprint. We're working on the project's basic features and setting up the environment. Could you suggest some questions each team member could answer during our daily Scrum meetings that would take about 5 minutes each?"

Expected Response: A set of questions focused on current tasks, challenges, and progress updates.

Planning Sprint and Backlog

Prompt: "We're developing a mobile application designed to help tourists explore Oslo by creating personalized visit plans. The app will have features like registration, geolocation, visit plans, and notifications. Can you help us develop a detailed product backlog with user stories and define the goals for our first two sprints? We aim to have geolocation and visit plan features ready as our MVP by the end of sprint two."

Expected Response: A structured backlog list with prioritized items and clearly defined goals for the initial sprints.

Improving Poorly Defined PBI (Product Backlog Item)

Prompt: "Our PO provided a draft user story about that seems vague and lacks clear acceptance criteria: *As a tourist, I want a map feature in the app to help me see places and stuff around Oslo, so I can get around easier.* Could you help me refine this user story to meet Scrum standards and suggest appropriate acceptance criteria?"

Expected Response: A revised PBI that is specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time boxed.

Creating DoD (Definition of Done) Criteria

Prompt: "My team need to establish a good Definition of Done for our sprint goal, focusing on aspects like code quality, user acceptance testing, and documentation. Could you assist in formulating these criteria?"

Expected Response: Criteria that include code quality standards, user acceptance testing, and documentation requirements.

Managing Risks

Prompt: "Considering the complexity of geolocation and visit planning features, I'm concerned that two sprints may not be enough to deliver our Minimum Viable Product. Can you identify potential risks and suggest mitigation strategies? Would adding an additional sprint be a potential solution?"

Expected Response: Identification of key risks like scope creep, technical debt, or resource constraints, with mitigation strategies.

Facilitating Scrum Ritual Adoption

Prompt: "My team prefers communication tools like Discord or Slack and often someone takes too long to respond and address an issue. I need ideas on how to motivate a transition towards adopting daily Scrum meetings."

Expected Response: Tips and strategies to encourage engagement and consistent participation in daily scrums.

Tracking Velocity and Progress

Prompt: "We're three days away from the end of our first two-week sprint, and we still have 10 story points left to meet our sprint goal. Here is our Scrumwise burndown chart. Could you help me assess

our team's velocity and estimate if we are on track?"

Prompt: "What is my current velocity?"

Expected Response: A burndown chart interpretation with analysis on whether the team is on track to meet sprint goals.

Resolving Conflicts

Prompt: "Two team members often discuss over coding standards, such as variable names and whether to use spaces or tabs. They never reach an agreement. Could you recommend some strategies to resolve these types of conflicts in a Scrum project?"

Expected Response: Conflict resolution techniques focusing on communication, mediation, and problem-solving.

Summarizing a Retrospective

Prompt: "We've just finished our first sprint retrospective where the team proposed improvements like scheduling daily meetings at 9 AM and standardizing on tabs for indentation. Some issues were put on hold for future discussion, like code commits without testing. Can you help summarize these outcomes and future action from this retrospective?"

Expected Response: A concise summary highlighting key feedback points and specific actions to improve future sprints.

Conclusion (5 minutes)

Copilot could also automate routine tasks, such as updating Scrum boards, which frees up the Scrum Master to focus more on team dynamics. Additionally, it could offer predictive analytics to foresee bottlenecks, and as virtual coaching for real-time problem-solving. Moreover, Copilot could support continuous learning and development, aligned to this course's activities.

AI relies heavily on the quality and extent of the data it's trained on, potentially leading to biased responses if the data is flawed. Moreover, AI cannot replicate the nuanced understanding and expertise of human managers. Therefore, AI should be used as a supportive tool rather than a replacement for human on decision-making.

This session began with an introduction to Copilot's capabilities as a generative AI tool, and how it can help tasks within Scrum. The session covered practical tasks, such as setting up daily Scrums, planning sprints, refining PBIs, and creating a Definition of Done. We also handled risk management, facilitating Scrum adoption, tracking project velocity, and address conflict resolution. The tutorial aimed to provide you, students with theoretical understanding and practical experiences using AI technologies.

As AI continues to advance, its applications in project management can enhance effectiveness. You're inspired to think creatively about how these tools can be used to particular needs, and challenges. By experimenting with AI, you can gain a competitive edge and develop new skills for your future careers.

Please remember to save your prompts for further reflection!